

Milestone:

MS12 - Production user portal deployed, with discoverability and data access functionality

Lead Participant:

PNED

Author:

Bruno Pacheco

Due:

31st October 2025

Date Of Completion:

6th November 2025

Means of Verification

Link to the test environment of the Catalogue :

- Portal: <https://portal.gdi.lu/>
- DAAMS: <https://daam.portal.gdi.lu/>
- Dataset Catalogue: <https://catalogue.portal.gdi.lu/>

Link to the documentation:

<https://genomicdatainfrastructure.github.io/gdi-userportal-frontend/>

Link to the open source codebase of the catalogue (everything with gdi-userportal prefix): <https://github.com/GenomicDataInfrastructure>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

No

Project participants & others

WP4 leads: Christophe Trefois, Wei Gu

User portal PO: Bruno Pacheco

FAIR Datapoint PO: Hans-Christian van der Werf

Beacon Network PO: Jordi Rambla

LS-AAI PO: Martin Kuba

REMS PO: Meeri Hakala

User portal Implementation team: Inderpal Singh, Rose Passigna, Rania Hamdani, Alessandro Merola, Emiliana Pali, Aleksandar Kmetov, Seha Artuç

FDP/Metadata Implementation team: Sean Berrie, Quinten Plevier, Ana Konrad, Kees Burger

Next action steps

- Improve support to Harmonised Metadata Model.
- Implement 1+MG look and feel.
- Implement RBAC for User Portal.
- Improve Allele Frequency Browser.

